

**make
a
thek**

**Deliverable D1.2
Data Management
Plan**

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Revision of History

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AUSSDA	Austrian Social Science Data Archive
BIPOC	Black, Indigenous, and People of Color
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC-BY License	A CC-BY license, also known as Creative Commons Attribution, allows others to use, adapt, and distribute your work, even commercially, as long as they give you credit for the original creation. It's the most open and flexible of the Creative Commons licenses.
CDO	Communication, Dissemination and Outreach
CO	Confidential
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FCF	Sihtasutus Fab City Foundation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LGBTQIA+	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender and Queer
OER	Open Educational Resources
PII	Personal Identifiable Information
PL2030	Public Libraries 2030
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
UMA	Ukrainian Makers Association
WP	Work Package
WP1	Management 1
WP2	Management 2
WP3	Mapping and Community Activation

WP4	Modular Makerspace Approach
WP5	Capacity Development
WP6	Community Engagement
WP7	European Public Library Pilots
WP8	Exploitation and Sustainability
WP9	CDO1 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1)
WP10	CDO2 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 2)
WP11	Impact Assessment
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH

Executive Summary

make-a-thek aims to establish modular, replicable makerspace set-ups within public libraries, offering open access to innovative and circular approaches in fashion and crafts. Grounded in extensive mapping and participatory co-creation, the project will develop a comprehensive resource toolkit and a suite of open educational resources (OERs) tailored for fashion- and craft-focused makerspaces in libraries. These will be piloted in at least nine European and three international library locations.

Throughout these pilot trials, communities of practitioners and prosumers (engaged citizens) will co-design and test new models for integrating traditional heritage crafts with digital fabrication techniques. This process will foster the exchange and development of tools, skills, techniques, and cultural practices that promote circularity in fashion and crafts.

Responsible data management is crucial for any innovation action and the Data Management Plan (DMP) provides structured guidelines for this process. The DMP covers the lifecycle of data, including the process of collection to storage, analysis and preservation. In this DMP we provide a basic description of what kind of data will be produced and collected during the course of *make-a-thek*, and details about what will happen to the data both during this project and after it has been completed.

make-a-thek is defining open access to research data as part of its open science approach and is thus committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during that process. Although the general policy of the *make-a-thek* project is to apply “open by default” to its data, we have to handle privacy issues with special care. Legal rules on anonymity are highly relevant and need to be agreed upon with each of the participants. Most of the data in *make-a-thek* will be anonymised data, but in case of a doubt, the data privacy of our participants always prevails over open data policy. When dealing with personal data, *make-a-thek* is making sure that all GDPR rules are followed, including e.g. data minimisation, which states that data has to be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed.

Overall, the leading framework for our data management is the GDPR in terms of personal data protection, FAIR data for the handling of non-personal data and Open Access following the European Union’s Open Science Guidelines.

This handbook is conceived as a **living document**. It will be updated as needed to reflect improvements, adapt to new challenges, and further enhance internal coordination and quality throughout the project.

1. Introduction

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of most research projects that collect or handle original data. This DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the make-a-thek project, following the Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice¹. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- the handling of original data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)

This document provides a first version of the DMP and includes all the information we have available at this point in time. As stated in the guidelines, the DMP is intended to be a living document in which information on data managed in the make-a-thek project can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur.

Therefore, we will implement this deliverable as a document that can be updated by the partner organisations at any time in the course of the project. In preparation for the mid-term review we will also reflect on the status of the DMP with the whole consortium and address any possible needs for updating the document and the processes described in it.

As described in the project handbook (D1.1) make-a-thek is committed to the integrative concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), which clearly goes beyond a pure ethical aspect. The importance of the RRI approach for make-a-thek is to align the co-creation process, which is an integral part of most activities, in a reflective way that is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other. So as to ensure alignment with RRI, the project will develop several activities around a reflective RRI process for all its stakeholders, as summarised within the Project Handbook.

By involving different stakeholders in our project activities may touch on sensitive ethical issues, respectively the protection of (possibly) sensitive private data. The Project Handbook (D1.1 published in Month 3), the ethics deliverables D9.1 and D9.2, and this document describes in detail how make-a-thek actors intend to collaborate when collecting, processing and handling data and handling privacy and security issues. All work packages will look specifically into all ethical and

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7738501#.ZBfwoC9XZQY>

legal issues related to the data they are dealing with, and a responsible Data Protection Officer (DPO) has been assigned (see Deliverable 9.2).

Project partners are aware of these sensitive issues and will build on ongoing European and African work on the management of trust and codes of conduct.

2. Data Summary

What kind of data is handled by this project and what is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? In the following we list the main characteristics that describe data and that we have applied to describe our make-a-thek data in Table 2 (at the end of this document).

Type of data

Following the Data Management Plan of previous projects, especially the mAKE project, which was praised for its exemplary data management plan (Kieslinger 2024), the following types of data may be collected and documented in research projects:

- **Observational:** data captured through observation of an activity and/or a behaviour in real-time (and, therefore, usually irreplaceable). The collection will require human observation, ethnography, and potentially also instruments, including surveys, interviews, focus groups, to record the information.
- **Experimental:** data obtained in controlled situations through the active intervention of researchers, who design an activity (called the experiment) to collect data. Such data can be reproduced if needed, but it may be time-consuming and expensive.
- **Simulational:** data generated through reproduction of a real-world system, usually used to determine what would happen in certain conditions.
- **Derived or Compiled:** data derived upon transformation of existing datasets to create new data. Such data can be reproduced if lost, but it is very time-consuming and it could be expensive.
- **Reference or Canonical:** to data used to categorise and/or classify other data. They could be static or changing over time.
- **Event-related:** data collected during events. As they are derived from real-time events, the data are irreplaceable. If they include personal data of participants, just as in the other types of data, the GDPR will be applied.

While most of the research data can be assigned to one of these categories in some cases there could also be an overlap. Some data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself (e.g. event-related data could also be considered observational data under certain conditions).

Reuse of existing data and origin of data

Next to the collection of genuinely new datasets, research work can also rely on existing data and generate new collections out of existing data sources (= derived or compiled data; sometimes also referred to as secondary data). The reuse of existing data sources will thus also be identified as well as the origin of the data to be used in the research process.

Format of the data and estimated size

Our data can have various formats: text, numeric, multimedia, models, software languages, codes and design, discipline and instrument specific, etc. It is important to describe the format of the data in order to facilitate its accessibility and interoperability. Preference will be given to open and standard formats. Likewise, data management experts advise to give indications about the size of the data collected in a DMP. Similar to the format of the data, size is relevant for future data-sharing and making data accessible. Over time information about the size of the managed data in make-a-thek should be revised and updated accordingly.

Aim of the data and the process of data collection

Part of the data description will always be the aim of the data produced, and how it is linked to the objectives of the project. Similarly, a short description of the process of the data collection will be applied so as to help to characterise the specific data.

In Table 2 at the end of this document we describe the make-a-thek data in as much detail as we can at this stage of the project. We remain cognisant of all the points outlined above, and we will update Table 2 (see Annex) in case of additional data being handled in any of our research activities.

3. FAIR Data

FAIR data means that the data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. In this section we elaborate on the measures the project is taking to generate FAIR data during the course of the project and to ensure FAIR use of the data beyond the project timeframe.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Versioning

The datasets produced in make-a-thek will follow good research practice by following a set of naming and versioning conventions, which are very useful for collaborative projects. A version control system will be applied to make sure that the data is organised and we can track back among different versions of the datasets. Such a version control system, which is also sometimes referred to as a revision control system, tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files over time. Google Docs, which is used for non-data-sensitive text editing, utilises a version history feature for version control, allowing users to track changes, revert to previous states, and manage different versions of a document. The system automatically saves snapshots of the document at various points in time, enabling users to easily navigate and restore previous versions. Through this version control system, make-a-thek will minimise the risk of losing information after modifications in collaborative processes where many make-a-thek consortium members are working with the data.

Naming

For the naming of our shareable data we will use file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines in order to make the data accessible and findable. Names must be meaningful, on the one hand, in order to make it easy for others to understand what the file contains and how it should be used. On the other hand, the names should use deliberate delimits in order to be machine readable. A common approach is using “_” and “-” to delimit units of metadata in the file names. For this project we will aim to use “-” to separate words we want to glob together, and “_” to separate different information within a file name. What we aim to avoid are blank spaces, punctuation, upper-casing of entire words, or special characters (e.g. characters such as \$, @, %, #, &*, (,), !, etc., which may have meanings in programming languages).

As mentioned above the file-naming should also always include a version number to make sure others who want to make use of any dataset know that they are dealing with which version. An example of an appropriate name for a data file is:

make-a-thek_D1-1_Project_handbook_v1

Metadata and keywords

Descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in a readme.txt file complementing each dataset (see Table 2). This detailed documentation should help interested users to clearly understand and reuse the data.

Table 1: Metadata for make-a-thek datasets

Title	Description
Creator(s)	Main person(s) involved in producing the data.
Title	Name or title by which the dataset is known.
Contributor(s)	Person(s) or organisation(s) responsible for making contributions to the dataset.
Publisher	Holder of the data (e.g. in archives), or person or institution who submitted the work.
Data ownership	Indication of primary data controller (person) and indication of additional data ownership, especially in the case of shared ownership.
Year of publication	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Data created	The date when the resource itself was put together (could be a date range or a single date)
Description	Concise description of the contents of the dataset. Describe the research objective, type of research, method of data collection, type of data and storage location of data (especially in the case of data not available on Zenodo).
Subject	Subject, or key phrase describing the resource.
Temporal coverage	The dates to which the data refer (the year or beginning and ending dates).
Spatial coverage	The geographic area to which the data refer (e.g. municipality, town/city, region, country). The geographic coordinates of the area may be included, if desired.
Identifier(s)	Zenodo automatically assigns a DOI to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. In some cases, a dataset may be known by one or more (persistent) identifier(s).
Language	The primary language of the resource.
Link to related publication(s)	Include the web addresses or DOIs for any publication, important internal reports or other datasets that are related to your dataset.
Keywords	Keywords that associate with the data resource.

As Table 1 shows, each data resource will have a unique identifier, e.g. a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). As we are committed to sharing all our open data on Zenodo, a DOI will be generated automatically and this will serve as our main data identifier. For some data, such as the open educational resources of WP5, we will apply a more detailed metadata schema, based on the DataCite Metadata Schema:

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.4.pdf

3.2. Making data openly accessible

General rules regarding accessibility

make-a-thek consortium members support the objective of opening up access to research results. Where applicable, the make-a-thek members are going to use open source licenses for software and non-exclusive licenses for other intellectual property rights such as copyrights, patents or standardisation proposals. Also, access to the collected data will be open and free while adhering to privacy and personal data protection. Peer-reviewed scientific publications that result from the project will be provided via open access (“gold” model). We will also consider submitting our publications to Open Research Europe (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>), the open access publishing platform for scientific articles launched by the European Commission as a free service for H2020 beneficiaries.

Issues related to protecting intellectual property are highly important when citizens and volunteers are involved in the work. The Consortium Agreement (CA) (signed by all consortium members before the project start) is the place where the details of management of intellectual property rights, including open licenses, between partners are defined. The CA also includes a list of pre-existing know-how (according to the description of work) and knowledge as well as the major principles on exploitation and dissemination issues. The consortium members have already agreed that access rights on the pre-existing know-how needed for carrying out the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

Research data access

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners, i.e., all data except where there is sensitive data that requires being kept only by the partner having collected the data. As described in the Project Handbook, the main workflow for data sharing starts at the work package (WP) level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/task team members are also responsible for any data anonymisation or pseudonymisation, if applicable. The data accessible to the whole consortium will be stored on the shared Nextcloud server provided by ZSI. Only members of the

consortium, after validation by the coordinator (Barbara Kieslinger), can access this space. The public data will be accessible via Zenodo.

Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes will be stored in the secure facilities of the organisation responsible for collecting the data and will be retained for two years after the end of project. Data containing personal identifiable information of individuals will only be shared, when necessary, based on a confidentiality agreement (see Annex of the Project Handbook). A data exchange form, signed by the partners exchanging sensitive data, documents the data exchange between these partners. This form is also provided in the Project Handbook.

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of project results are defined in section 8 of the Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 26(2), Article 29(1) and Article 30, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

Sensitive Social Science Data

In make-a-thek we are dealing with quantitative and qualitative social science data (see Table 2 below), which is often context-sensitive data that includes personal data. GDPR applies for any such personal data, defined as follows:

‘personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person; (Art. 4(1), GDPR)

Thus we have to pay careful attention not only to avoiding direct identifiers in our data, but also indirect identifiers that could make persons identifiable through aggregation of information. For special categories of personal data it may even be necessary to provide for certain suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject. Protection of data subjects according to GDPR rules will take clear precedence over our commitment and intention to contribute as much as possible to open research. If necessary, we may also apply data encryption to make sure sensitive personal data is protected.

There are certain measures that can be taken to allow even highly qualitative social scientific data to be made available and shareable, and we will make use of these measures as far as possible. This includes e.g. clear procedures for informed consent (see our Project Handbook for details), anonymisation, pseudonymisation (see deliverable 9.2. For more details), and/or access restrictions.

We will eliminate direct and indirect identifiers through one or more of the following:

- Deleting certain information
- Substituting personal identifiers with pseudonyms (more relevant for qualitative data, e.g. interview transcripts)

- Aggregating the information (more relevant for quantitative data, e.g. numeric dataset)

The Austrian Social Science Data Archive (AUSSDA) offers support for data pseudonymisation via pseudonymisation checks. As the ZSI is a collaboration partner of AUSSDA we can make use of this service for our make-a-thek research data. Still, if we anonymise the data to make it shareable we have to ask ourselves the question of how far the sharing of this qualitative and often highly context sensitive data makes sense and how far this data could then still be reused by others.

If we allow restricted access to the research data to enable data sharing for scientific purposes we will follow the principle of “as open as possible - as closed as necessary”. Such restricted access could be granted to a predefined group of users or to certain accounts and under certain conditions. Within the consortium we also have a data sharing agreement in order to exchange research data within the consortium. Such restricted access would only be granted to consortium-external researchers with the consent of the research subjects.

In cases where datasets can be made freely available as they do not include any personalised data we will make them available with the corresponding metadata on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

3.3. Making data interoperable

The interoperability of the data mostly depends on the metadata that is provided with the data. Table 1 above described the general metadata that we will provide with each of our datasets. In addition, Zenodo requires metadata for the description of any data shared on the portal. This metadata uses a vocabulary that follows the FAIR data principles and that offers export options to international standard formats, such as Dublin Core or the Datacite Metadata Schema, to make the data interoperable.

To allow inter-disciplinary interoperability we plan to use standard vocabularies for all data types present in your datasets. However, there may be uncommon vocabularies being used that stem from the maker-specific context in which we are operating. These context-specific vocabularies may require provision of some additional explanation with the data, in order to make them interoperable across disciplines.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

The main users of data produced in the project will be the consortium partners. Following an open and participatory approach towards data sharing and re-use, we also consider participants in our project activities as potential users of the collected data. All data will be classified as open, sensitive or closed, with the access and re-usability depending on the classification. For re-use of the data the following applies:

- Open data will be freely available, subject to the user acknowledging it through citing the name and creator of the dataset. Permission from the main data creator (main researcher) or contributors is not required.
- Sensitive (or confidential/restricted data) may be made available by the data creator after any identifying information has been removed. Reuse of this anonymised/pseudonymised data may be possible, if cited and if agreed to by the dataset creator and its contributors.
- Closed data are not available for sharing or reuse.

The open data generated in this project will carry the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license so as to permit its reuse. As previously mentioned, all relevant open data will be preserved and archived in Zenodo. As far as we can say at this point, all data and items on Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. There is currently no intention to remove the shared data from the repository at any given time. Zenodo is hosted by CERN which has an experimental programme defined for the next 20+ years, offering long-term accessibility of the data.

4. Other Research Output

Next to the research data, make-a-thek will ensure open access to other project outputs. All deliverables labelled as “public” will be made accessible via the make-a-thek website. The publications stemming from the project work will also be made available on the website as long as it does not infringe the publishers’ rights as well as on the Zenodo platform.

All outcomes of the project, including design, protocols, toolkits, prototypes, etc. that are labelled as “public” will be distributed under a specific free/open license, where the authors retain the authors’ rights but the users can redistribute the content freely.

5. Allocation of Resources

make-a-thek’s open data management is part of Task T1.5 and T2.5 of the Management WPs, under the lead of the coordinator ZSI. All other consortium partners are committed to contributing to the data management in their roles as WP leaders.

Thus, the main workflow starts at the WP level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/working team members are also responsible for any data anonymisation, if applicable. An agreement has to be reached within the team for making any outcome openly available; the final approval is done by the Work Package Leader Group.

Figure: Open Access workflow

As outlined in the Project Handbook, this Data Management Plan may have to be revised over the course of project activities. As the co-design approach that make-a-thek is following is a rather dynamic methodology, it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes from the beginning.

The costs for making any of our research data FAIR can be covered by the project budget during the official funding period. According to the Grant Agreement, costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

6. Data Security

6.1. Data storage

In make-a-thek we have two main storage locations for our data:

Google Drive: Used for file sharing and collaborative, real-time document editing. This is used for sharing non-sensitive data.

Basecamp: Hosted by PL2030, Basecamp serves as the primary internal project space for secure document exchange and storage. All data uploaded and shared on Basecamp is encrypted using AES-256/ SHA-256 encryption.

Partners secured servers: Research partners in make-a-thek may use their own servers to store any sensitive data collected during the project activities.

Research data shared between the researchers across institutions may contain personal identifiable information (PII), the usage of which is protected by law. To comply with this law, usage, and sharing of data is restricted and it is essential that every partner follows the rules and guidelines described in the ethical guidelines defined for make-a-thek for collecting, processing, sharing, and storage of data. For the exchange of data, a data exchange form has been provided in the project handbook. It regulates the exchange between partners regarding sensitive data and is available in the Project Handbook (Annex).

The coordinator ZSI can store data on their server, which is fully GDPR compliant. ZSI is running its own IT infrastructure, and its IT staff takes great care to ensure data security and protection via these measures, among others:

- in-house servers controlled exclusively by ZSI IT staff
- services running in a demilitarised network zone behind a redundant firewall
- resource isolation for services through hardware nodes and/or virtual machines
- regular updates of system and application software
- timely installation of security patches from OSS suppliers
- daily backups, off-site backup on encrypted hard disks, monitoring and logging
- web server hardening
- a password policy
- consultation and awareness-raising with ZSI staff on data protection issues
- precautions for emergency scenarios
- compliance with GDPR

Consortium partners may also store the data they generate on their own secure servers, making sure that secure storage is guaranteed. The conditions for transfer of any sensitive data are described above and in the Project Handbook.

Under no circumstance will make-a-thek collect, store or process private information, etc. without the explicit and written permission of the respective persons. make-a-thek will comply fully with data protection provisions as set out in the currently applicable Data Protection Directive EC 95/46, the General Data Protection Regulation EU/2016/679 (GDPR) and the e-Privacy Directive EC 2002/58 (confidentiality of information, treatment of traffic data, spam and cookies).

6.2. Data retention

As indicated above, make-a-thek will make the research data openly accessible as widely as possible. This means that the data is available on open repositories under FAIR principles (see above) and there is no specific retention foreseen from the project side for the open access research data.

For the personal (sensitive) data collected during the course of the project make-a-thek will keep the data only as long as necessary for the implementation of the specific action and needs to be deleted right afterwards without delay.

For reporting purposes partners must keep records and other supporting documents to prove the proper implementation of the work and/or achievement of the results as described in Annex 1 at least for 5 years. This refers to original documents as outlined in the Grant Agreement. In addition, national regulations may apply and need to be considered individually by partners.

Here is a short summary overview of the retention period according to the different data categories:

6.3. Data deletion

According to GDPR individuals have the right to ask for their data to be deleted. This is also stated in the make-a-thek informed consent form. Thus, at any time, if an individual asks for their data being removed this has to be done by the partner managing the data.

In addition, in case an individual asks to be removed from online published information where they previously agreed, make-a-thek partners need to remove this information. Following the right to be forgotten online, partners are expected to take reasonable steps (for example technical measures) to inform other websites that a particular individual has requested the erasure of their personal data.

Where possible, data can also be kept if it has undergone an appropriate process of anonymisation according to GDPR.

7. Responsible Research and Innovation Aspects

Research must respect ethical standards and fundamental rights to respond to societal challenges.

During the lifetime of the project, make-a-thek will continuously follow an approach that ensures an appropriate level of ethical sensitivity, meaning that any changes and implementations will be viewed from an ethical perspective and (where needed) actions taken accordingly. Those consortium members that are research performing organisations have internal ethical boards and will seek their approval for any data sensitive activities.

The Project Handbook describes in detail the ethical standards we apply for our research , which are aligned with our principles of responsible research.

Gender equality and gender diversity

The make-a-thek project fully supports the European Union policy on equal opportunities between women, men and gender-diverse persons. To this end,

participation of all genders will be continually encouraged and supported. Project staff of all consortium members are composed according to the principle of equal opportunity and all member organisations strongly enforce an equal opportunity policy in their human resources selection processes.

In make-a-thek we are aware that the public perception may still be that crafts and especially in fashion, attracts a dominantly cis-female audience, while the maker communities are still strongly cis-male dominated. The gender spectrum is much broader though and make-a-thek wants to embrace this plurality. Studies have identified factors that contribute to more gender inclusiveness in maker settings and also consider the impact of intersectional inequalities. We will work further on those aspects and consider different effects of our work and the participation in the co-design according to gender in our analysis. The engagement activities of our participatory approach address all genders and we will seek to define activities in gender inclusive settings and apply gender inclusive language and training material.

At the impact assessment level, gender dimensions will be considered during the analytical phase to assess whether co-designing engagement activities reproduce gender stereotypes or whether, in an appropriate setting, co-designing can contribute to supporting gender diversity. Also, it should be stressed that gender is not regarded as a binary concept in our project, but rather fluid and we aim to explore opportunities for all genders. We are aware of inherent gender and cultural biases and will follow a culturally and gender-sensitive methodology with cultural and gender equality-sensitive principles. For all project activities the consortium will do its utmost to have a balanced gender distribution for e.g. interviews, workshops, co-design sessions, and stakeholder encounters.

Fostering inclusion and diversity in engagement activities, co-design and educational content

make-a-thek aims to be beneficial for all, and inclusive from a social point of view, creating new opportunities, bringing inspiration, training and business development also for all those population groups generally outside the circuits of innovation. For make-a-thek, inclusion also means producing informative and educational content accessible by craftspeople from different sectors and with different levels of knowledge and technical or technological skills, including those without formal education and ancestral training. The mapping, collecting and sharing process of traditional techniques wants to value and preserve the different traditions and skills, including and embracing socio-cultural diversity as an element of global enrichment. As make-a-thek will facilitate local and global exchange, contributing to cultural exchange between craft makers around the world. Our global activities will include craft makers of indigenous origins.

Bottom-up co-design approaches involve collaborating with citizens and communities to envision designs tailored to their local context. This method engages citizens in the creation process, fostering empowerment and agency, thereby bridging the gap between people's capabilities and their involvement in

shaping their environment. This inclusive approach counters the tendency to exclude citizens and communities from the design process, contributing to the development of more holistic, diverse, and inclusive solutions that effectively address real-life challenges. make-a-thek advocates for an environment that reaches new groups, especially vulnerable or historically excluded ones, acknowledging the historical gatekeeping in design and other fields. Our belief is in re-centering historically excluded individuals and underrepresented communities, including those who are BIPOC, LGBTQIA+, migrants, have disabilities, previous experience with the justice system, and others at the intersection of these identities, ensuring their meaningful inclusion in our work. The choice to implement the pilots in public libraries aims to enhance the inclusion of vulnerable groups and groups that are not part of any formal education system. Public libraries are non-commercial, open and safe spaces facilitating learning and exchange between various groups of people.

8. Summary and Outlook

This document, together with the Project Handbook (D1.1), describes the main aspects of how this project will practice open research and how we will handle our research data. While make-a-thek is fully committed to open science and openness as defaults, the privacy and data security of personal data coming from our research participants is of the highest priority. Templates and procedures for data collection, including for ethical compliance, are in place and will be reflected in the consortium.

As research data management is a continuous process and we can currently not foresee all eventualities that may arise through following an open co-design methodology, we will reflect on and update this DMP in the course of the project.

9. References

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Annex - Data Description of make-a-thek

Table 2: Data overview

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP3_Research Mapping	Identification of key players/stakeholders, including email addresses to contact the relevant initiatives	derived or compiled	xlsx	compilation of data pre-existing from different sources; Use of data compiled by the project
WP3_Community Activation Sessions	Participant lists: Name, Organisation, Email address Pictures of participants provide proof of participation at events funded through EC	event-related	pdf jpeg	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP3_Surveys	<p>Aim: collect insights to support the design and development of m-a-t modular approach</p> <p>Data description: demographic information, educational and professional backgrounds, engagement with creative spaces, and perspectives on circular practices. It helps identify needs, habits, and opportunities for collaboration among librarians, makers, crafters, designers, and citizens</p>	compiled	xlsx, jpeg	<p>No reuse of pre-existing data</p> <p>Use of data compiled by the project</p>
WP4_Co-design	<p>Aim: Online Interviews to librarians to understand needs and opportunities</p> <p>Data description: Name, Organisation, Email address, role in the organisation, personal opinions, interviews notes and audio/video recording</p>	observational	mp4, docx, jpeg, pdf	<p>No reuse of pre-existing data</p> <p>Use of data compiled by the project</p>
WP4_Co-design	<p>Aim: Research to increase the knowledge about libraries and their users</p> <p>Data description: Data collected from previous user analysis by the libraries, social-environmental studies, user personas</p>	derived or compiled	docx, xlsx, pdf	New compilation of data collected by libraries to assess the status quo and users behaviours

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
	studies, researches by marketing and communications teams within the libraries			
WP4_Co-design	<p>Aim: Co-design event to understand tools, users and activities within the libraries</p> <p>Data description: Name, Organisation, Email address, role in the organisations, personal opinions</p> <p>pictures of participants, notes,</p>	event-related	xlsx, png, jpeg, pdf, mp4	<p>No reuse of pre-existing data</p> <p>Use of data compiled by the project</p>
WP4_Co-design	<p>Test of the make-a-thek approach / digital toolkit</p> <p>Live and online feedback recording</p>	<p>observational</p> <p>simulational</p> <p>experimental</p>	xlsx, png, jpeg, pdf, mp4	<p>No reuse of pre-existing data</p> <p>Use of data compiled by the project</p>

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP5_Interviews, desk research mapping & Surveys	Knowledge, skills and resources (gaps) for a first iteration of a Skills and Competencies Compass	derived or compiled	xlsx, PDF, web-based	Data derived and/or compiled by the project based on existing projects (Fabricademy, Facacademy etc) to make new compilation
WP5_List of experts and trainers	Identification of educators, trainers and experts for the T5.2 activities (building on WP3 Research Mapping and added on)	derived or compiled	xlsx	
WP5_Feedback form	Feedback form from workshop facilitators and participants to understand which MAT activities were successful, how to improve and which additional learning materials to develop.	event-related, derived or compiled, observational data	xlsx, PDF, JPEG	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP5_Links to learning materials	Links to learning materials (via QR codes or similar) in the form of audio files, videos hosted on streaming platform, or documentation materials hosted in online repositories	derived or compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, SVG, PNG, Audio files [mp3 / mp4], Video, Markdown, OBJ, HTML, ZIP	Data derived and/or compiled by the project and based on existing projects (Fabricademy, Facacademy

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
				etc) to make new compilation
WP6_Community member mobility	Data on travel departure location and mobility location, Bank account details for budget transfer, mini experience reports collected from participants	derived or compiled	xlsx, PDF, JPEG	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP6_Knowledge Exchange insights	Participants reflections gathered in a mini-experience report, audio files or video recordings.	event-related, derived or compiled, observational data	DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP6_Community learning journeys	Participants reflections gathered in a mini-experience report, audio files or video recordings.	event-related, derived or compiled, observational data	DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP7 - preparation of pilot contracts	Financial and bank information for transfer of funds to pilot libraries	Organisational Financial information	DOC	NO

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP7 - hosting in person meetings	Information necessary to facilitate travel and participation of partners Passport numbers, personal information, phone numbers and emails	Event-related	DOC/EXL	NO
WP8_City Level Dialogues w/ policymakers, community representatives, and relevant stakeholders	Records from city-level dialogues in the 9 pilot cities, aimed at capturing insights and recommendations for integrating makerspaces, and circular making principles into urban planning. Supports the development of policy recommendations and a policy paper for city governments.	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	DOCX (report, policy paper); Notes (notes); JPEG (event photos).	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP9/10 KPIs- Communication & Dissemination Outreach	Social media statistics Google analytics for the website	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	XLSX/spreadsheets, DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP9/10_Communication & Dissemination Outreach	Newsletter: Name and contact details of subscribers	Derived or Compiled	Collected in Mailchimp	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP10_Final Impact Event	registration data, filming, posts, etc.	Observational Derived - Compiled	XLSX/spreadsheets, DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP9/10_KPIs - Communication & Dissemination Outreach	Collect data through Events Tracker for Public Events created by/participated by Consortium Partners Name and contact details of Consortium Partners Interviews with Consortium Partners	Event-related Derived - Compiled	XLSX/spreadsheets DOC/DOCX/ODT PDF JPEG Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4] videos	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP9/10_KPIs - Communication & Dissemination Outreach	Photos for projects stock images Name and signature of individuals in the photos consenting to image use.	Event-related Derived - Compiled	JPG, png, psd, pdf	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data* (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP11_Interviews with professional participants/implementors at pilot events	Collection of statements from professional participants (crafters, fashion experts, librarians, makers) in specific countries; the data will be subject to the informed consent procedure described in D1.1 “Project Handbook”.)	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project
WP11_Interviews with diverse participants at pilot events	Collection of statements from interested participants, e.g. underrepresented groups, in specific countries; the data will be subject to the informed consent procedure described in D1.1 “Project Handbook”.)	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project